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Helmholtz Open Science Briefing

**Helmholtz Open Science
Forum on Open Research
Information**

Report

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Imprint

The online version of this publication can be found at:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16419876>

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published by

Helmholtz Open Science Office

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Status

August 1, 2025 | Version 1.0

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Abstract

Research information – data on research outputs and activities – is omnipresent and essential in everyday research, but is often not freely accessible. It is often collected by commercial providers who charge for access, while at the same time many research institutions produce vast amounts of research information with the potential of making it better accessible. Research information is also essential for fair and transparent research assessment, decision-making and resource allocation. Hence, its openness is of decisive relevance – as another important building block of open science, for the reform of research assessment and for academic sovereignty. An important milestone is the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information, which calls for open research information to become the norm. The Helmholtz Open Science Forum on Open Research Information on 2 April 2025 was dedicated to the topic of open research information and offered members of the Helmholtz Association a space for information and exchange. The forum covered an introduction on the Barcelona Declaration, presentations of activities within Helmholtz, and discussions between Helmholtz stakeholders on the state of research information and possible future activities within Helmholtz as well as on general challenges and opportunities of open research information.

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Introduction

Research information – data on research outputs and activities – is omnipresent and essential in everyday research, be it bibliographic metadata on publications and other research results, data on funding and projects or information on research institutions and researchers themselves. However, research information is often not freely accessible and usable. Research information is often collected by commercial providers and made available to the scientific community itself in return for payment, as in the case of the Web of Science and Scopus platforms. At the same time, while many research institutions produce vast amounts of research information, there is still potential in making this research information better accessible. And as research information is indispensable and crucial for strategic decisions, the allocation of resources, research evaluation and recruitment – in short, essential for fair and transparent research assessment –, the openness of such information is of decisive relevance. Open research information is therefore another important building block of open science practices and in the reform of research assessment as well as for academic sovereignty. The Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information published in April 2024 therefore aims to make open research information the norm.

This Helmholtz Open Science Forum on April 2, 2025 was dedicated to the topic of open research information and offered members of the Helmholtz Association a space for exchange and discussion. The forum opened with a keynote speech on the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information (by Bianca Kramer, executive director of the Barcelona Declaration), which was followed by an input from the Helmholtz Open Science Office and an input from the library of the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology. The forum was concluded by a moderated, open discussion session with the Helmholtz stakeholders. 50 participants (from 17 of the 18 Helmholtz centers) participated in the event.

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Program

Time	Program	Speaker
2:00 p.m.	Welcome and Introduction	Mathijs Vleugel Helmholtz Open Science Office, Head
2:10 p.m.	Keynote: Introducing the Barcelona Declaration	Bianca Kramer Barcelona Declaration, Executive Director / Sesame Open Science
2:30 p.m.	Open Research Information: Input from the Helmholtz Open Science Office	Marc Lange Helmholtz Open Science Office
2:45 p.m.	Open Research Information: Insights from a Helmholtz Center	Arne Upmeier & Maria Nüchter Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Library
3:00 p.m.	Discussion (breakout sessions & plenary discussion)	all participants moderation: Mathijs Vleugel & Marc Lange Helmholtz Open Science Office
3:55 p.m.	Closing Remarks	Mathijs Vleugel Helmholtz Open Science Office, Head

Presentations

Keynote: Introducing the Barcelona Declaration

Bianca Kramer, executive director of the Barcelona Declaration and working at Sesame Open Science, gave a keynote that introduced the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information. The presentation set out by defining research information as (bibliographic) metadata, including funding information and information on use and impact, and stating its relevance for various selection, decision making and assessment processes in science. Consequently, research information must be open, as stated in the four core commitments of the Barcelona Declaration. The current number of signatories and supporters and their geographic distribution and the Barcelona Declaration's timeline and activities so far were presented. The presentation further outlined the joint roadmap on open research information, addressing the initiated working groups in the seven main focus areas: 1. journal article and book metadata; 2. metadata for research outputs in institutional repositories, preprint repositories and data repositories; 3. funding metadata; 4. replacing closed systems; 5. sustainability of infrastructures; 6. evaluating open data sources; 7. evidence of benefits. The presentation concluded with guiding questions and suggestions regarding the promotion of open research information and signing the Barcelona Declaration.

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Open Research Information: Input from the Helmholtz Open Science Office

Marc Lange from the Helmholtz Open Science Office (OS Office) gave an overview of the OS Office's participation in the activities of the Barcelona Declaration so far and on the status quo of research information in Helmholtz. After the release of the Barcelona Declaration in April 2024, the OS Office started coordination and early consultations within Helmholtz, took part in the Paris Conference on Open Research Information in September 2024 - hence, contributed to the joint roadmap on open research information - and initiated a community of practice among members from institutions in the German-speaking countries. It is also participating in four of the Barcelona Declaration working groups started from February 2025 on. As all the Helmholtz centers already generate, collect, use and provide research information, open research information is not an entirely new issue and some of the Barcelona Declaration's objectives are already met to certain degrees. Still, a more comprehensive understanding of open research information practices within Helmholtz is important. Giving examples of other institutions' activities in the domain of research information, the presentation concluded by pointing out important points of reference, potentials and challenges, as well as potential future actions within Helmholtz.

Open Research Information: Insights from a Helmholtz Center

Arne Upmeier and Maria Nüchter, both from the library of the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), gave insights from the KIT on open infrastructures for open research information. These comprise the open access publication infrastructure operated as KIT Scientific Publishing as well as the repository KITopen as a central data hub with inputs and outputs of different kinds of research information. Furthermore, two of KIT's current projects connected to research information were presented: Project ERRED ('Development of a reference model for reporting in scientific institutions using DORA'), which aims to develop an alternative model for evaluating scientific performance, and the project 'Open Science and FIS light', which comprises the use of a current research information system (CRIS) as a tool for managing information and reporting. In the latter regard, reporting, the presentation also focused on questions and challenges regarding the possibility of open bibliometrics. As a conclusion and a stimulus for the discussion, the presentation closed with an overview of the current state of KIT's activities regarding the Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA), the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) and the Barcelona Declaration.

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Discussion

The discussions in the breakout sessions showed that the participants from the Helmholtz centers generate, document and utilize a variety of research information, usually metadata on publications (text publications, research data and research software), people and organizations, but also funding information and metadata on research instruments, for example. Typical uses for research information are reporting, analysis, monitoring publications and grants, and management of research outputs. Work on improving workflows and data accessibility was mentioned, with potentials in better linking of different data sources and utilizing APIs. Used research information sources are primarily repositories and, to a lesser degree, CRIS systems of the centers. Also important are databases, most often Web of Science and Scopus and, less often, Dimensions and PubMed. Also frequently used are data sources usually used in connection with persistent identifiers, such as DataCite, Crossref, ORCID and the ROR. Directories (such as the Research Software Directory) and discipline-specific services were mentioned as other important sources. It was noted that spreadsheets are still a widely used source and tool, especially for reporting purposes.

Participants' responses on the state of open research information at their centers indicated that most centers are not yet in a position to fulfill all the commitments of the Barcelona Declaration. Nevertheless, the use of open alternatives was seen as preferable and some centers are already discussing and considering to do so, often in connection with the Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA) and the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA). Furthermore, while subscriptions to the proprietary data sources Web of Science and/or Scopus are currently still dominant, centers increasingly use open data sources and several centers are considering the use of OpenAlex¹ - on which they would welcome further exchange and alignment. Improved CRIS infrastructure and more standardized metadata were also perceived as vital for advancing open research information.

The plenary discussion revolved around future activities within Helmholtz and the challenges and opportunities of open research information. A key discussion point was the question of what information should be openly shared and with whom, balancing openness with institutional needs, data privacy and research security.² Concerns were raised about potential commercialization of open research information (for AI-driven trend analyses or research evaluation, for example). Underlying this was a discussion of data sovereignty, with a desire for institutions to maintain ownership and control over data originating from their researchers. Also discussed were the benefits of open research information for researchers (visibility, recognition), the importance of aligning open practices and research evaluation perspectives, and, last but not least, how OpenAlex as a source for research information can be built upon and likewise contributed to from within Helmholtz.

¹ See our Open Science Factsheet on OpenAlex: <https://doi.org/10.48440/os.helmholtz.046>

² It was clarified that there is no requirement by the Barcelona Declaration for all research information to be made available. However, if research information is made available, it should be open - or: as open as possible and as closed as necessary.

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Appendix: Presentation Slides

Keynote: Introducing the Barcelona Declaration

by Bianca Kramer (Barcelona Declaration, Executive Director / Sesame Open Science)

Open Research Information: Input from the Helmholtz Open Science Office

by Marc Lange (Helmholtz Open Science Office)

Open Research Information: Insights from a Helmholtz Center

by Arne Upmeier and Maria Nüchter (Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Library)

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BARCELONA DECLARATION ON OPEN RESEARCH INFORMATION

Bianca Kramer

Helmholtz Open Science Forum

2 April 2025

<https://tinyurl.com/bd-helmholtz-20250402>

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Open research information

Why is it important?

Research information

- Research information: (bibliographic) metadata - including funding information and information on use and impact
- Used in decision making around strategic priorities, distribution of resources, and evaluation of researchers and institutions
- Used to assess the effect of policies (funders, institutions, government)
- Used by researchers and societal stakeholders to find and assess research results

Research information must be open

Closed research information

We are assessing researchers and institutions based on **non-transparent evidence**...

We are making decisions based on information that is **biased against less privileged languages, geographical regions, and research agendas**...

We are monitoring and incentivizing open science using **closed data**...

— but —>

fair assessment requires full transparency

— but —>

equitable decision-making requires inclusive data

— but —>

open science requires open research information

Barcelona Declaration

barcelona-declaration.org

Barcelona Declaration - Commitments

As organizations that carry out, fund, and evaluate research, we commit to the following:

1

We will make openness the default for the research information we use and produce

2

We will work with services and systems that support and enable open research information

Barcelona Declaration - Commitments

As organizations that carry out, fund, and evaluate research, we commit to the following:

3

We will support the sustainability of infrastructures for open research information

4

We will support collective action to accelerate the transition to openness of research information

Barcelona Declaration - Signatories

BARCELONA DECLARATION ON OPEN RESEARCH INFORMATION

"CLACSO-FOLEC firmly advocates for research assessment methodologies that take advantage of the multiplicity of formats, languages and distribution channels of scientific knowledge. To this end we support the use of data that reflect both the production disseminated in international repositories and that which is hosted in regional and local databases."

Karina Batthyány
Executive Director CLACSO

BARCELONA DECLARATION ON OPEN RESEARCH INFORMATION

"The declaration is fully aligned with the 2021 European Council Conclusions, which were released under French Presidency. The Council conclusions indeed state that 'data and bibliographic databases used for research assessment should, in principle, be openly accessible and that tools and technical systems should enable transparency'. It is also very well aligned with the 2016 French Law that is commonly referred to as 'Digital Republic Law'."

Marin Dacos
French Coordinator for Open Science

BARCELONA DECLARATION ON OPEN RESEARCH INFORMATION

"Sorbonne University has strongly supported the move toward open science for many years and the implementation of open research practices and principles in all their dimensions within its community. Beyond its benefits for researchers and research institutions, this next step towards open research information is also a civic engagement for a more open, responsible and trustworthy university."

Nathalie Drach-Temam
President, Sorbonne University

BARCELONA DECLARATION ON OPEN RESEARCH INFORMATION

"We want research information that is easy to understand, handle, and analyse, while ensuring our analyses maintain transparency and reproducibility. Thankfully, we now have the necessary tools, processes, and determination to turn this vision into reality."

Paola Galimberti
Director of the Open Science Policy Division, University of Milan

BARCELONA DECLARATION ON OPEN RESEARCH INFORMATION

"Transparency and rigour are core to UKRN's mission. This is as important for research information as it is for research, and so we will actively support the aims of the Barcelona Declaration."

Marcus Munafò
Chair of the UK Reproducibility Network Supervisory Board

BARCELONA DECLARATION ON OPEN RESEARCH INFORMATION

"With Open Research Information we may review and access Open Science contributions in an open way. Indeed, we may make all our research assessment transparent and FAIR - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable - with Open Access and without any restrictions on how the Open Research Information is used and shared."

Mogens Sandfaer
Head of National Open Research Analytics, Denmark

Signatories and supporters

- As of today, the Barcelona Declaration has been **formally signed by 108 organizations in 26 countries**; among others, signatories include universities and other research institutions, research funders, and governments

Signatories and supporters

- As of today, the Barcelona Declaration has been **formally signed by 108 organizations in 26 countries**; among others, signatories include universities and other research institutions, research funders, and governments
- In addition, **50 organizations** providing data, services and infrastructure are **formal supporters** of the Declaration
- Many organizations have not yet signed the Declaration but have expressed an **interest in contributing to the transition to open research information**

German signatories

- **Universities and other research performing organizations**
 - Hamburg University of Technology (Germany)
 - Hugo Grotius GmbH
 - Knowmad Institut
 - Leibniz Association
 - Otto-Friedrich-Universität Bamberg
 - University of Göttingen
- **Other organizations**
 - DINI - Deutsche Initiative für Netzwerkinformation
 - FIZ Karlsruhe - Leibniz Institute for Information Infrastructure
 - TIB - Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology and University Library
 - ZPID - Leibniz Institute for Psychology

What are the next steps?

How do we make sure the **transition to open research information is truly going to happen?**

Paris Conference

September 23-24, 2024
Sorbonne University

130 participants
(on site and online)

Report of the Paris Conference on Open Research Information

September 23-24 2024, Sorbonne University, Paris

November 8, 2024 / <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14054244>

Paris conference

- **Share information and experiences** around adoption of open research information and implementation of the commitments

https://zenodo.org/communities/paris_conference_ori_2024

- **Develop a joint road map** of next steps that need coordination and collaboration between signatories and supporters.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14054244>

Collective actions - joint roadmap

- Journal article metadata
 - IR / preprint / data repository metadata
 - Funding metadata
 - Replacing closed systems
 - Sustainability of infrastructures
 - Evaluating open data sources
 - Evidence of benefits
- Working groups, coordinated by signatory organizations
 - Concrete outcomes over 6-24 months
 - Collaboration between signatories and supporters

Collective actions - joint roadmap

Things we don't know.
How much money?
Who is doing this?
How?

How does it all fit?
Where are the gaps
and challenges? What
works and where?

What can we agree
to do together?
Where are the places
for collective action?

How do we deliver
change? How do we test
progress and hold each
other accountable?

Information Gathering

- Surveys
- Case studies
- Sharing experiences

Frameworks & Analysis

- Develop
- Populate
- Quantitative and landscape analysis

Principles & Guidelines

- Develop
- Shared Commitment
- Plans for implementation

Implementation & Monitoring

- Deliver
- Monitor
- Critique, test and refine

Collective action - what do we have already?

- Talks from Paris
- Existing EC work
- UNESCO Open Science Outlook
- POSI/FOREST
- Limited landscape analysis
- POSI/FOREST
- FAIR/CARE
- CoARA
- OSMI
- Barcelona
- Pioneer institutions
- Testing metadata completeness
- ESAC
- SCOSS
- InfraFinder (IOI)

Information Gathering

- Surveys
- Case studies
- Sharing experiences

Frameworks & Analysis

- Develop
- Populate
- Quantitative and landscape analysis

Principles & Guidelines

- Develop
- Shared Commitment
- Plans for implementation

Implementation & Monitoring

- Deliver
- Monitor
- Critique, test and refine

Organization

Barcelona Declaration

- To draft the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information, a workshop was organized **in Barcelona in November 2023**, hosted by **SIRIS Foundation**
- **Over 25 research information experts**, representing organizations that carry out, fund, and evaluate research, as well as open infrastructure organizations, participated in the workshop
- Preparation of the Declaration was coordinated by **Bianca Kramer** (Sesame Open Science), **Cameron Neylon** (Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative, Curtin University), and **Ludo Waltman** (Centre for Science and Technology Studies, Leiden University)

Barcelona Declaration

- In January 2025, **CWTS**, **Crossref** and **SIRIS Foundation** signed an MOU to provide financial support to the Barcelona Declaration organization for 3 years
- Appointment of **Executive director** (Bianca Kramer) and **Community manager** (currently hiring)
- Steering group consisting of representatives of the 3 supporting organizations, **COKI** and **Sorbonne University** - until establishment of full Governance board
- Organizational goals: facilitate and support collective actions through working groups; dissemination and outreach activities to expand the reach and impact of the Declaration

Concluding questions

Concluding questions

1. Is your institute ready to sign the Barcelona Declaration?
2. What is the position of Helmholtz Association on openness of research information?
3. How can Helmholtz institutes work together to promote openness of research information?

BARCELONA DECLARATION ON OPEN RESEARCH INFORMATION

www.barcelona-declaration.org

The Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information was prepared by a group of over 25 research information experts, representing organizations that carry out, fund, and evaluate research, as well as organizations that provide research information infrastructures. The group met in Barcelona in November 2023 in a workshop hosted by SIRIS Foundation. The preparation of the Declaration was coordinated by Bianca Kramer (Sesame Open Science), Cameron Neylon (Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative, Curtin University), and Ludo Waltman (Centre for Science and Technology Studies, Leiden University). Organizations that would like to know more about the Declaration or that wish to sign the Declaration are welcome to reach out to contact@barcelona-declaration.org

Barcelona Declaration

Full commitments
All road map actions

Barcelona Declaration - Commitment 1

As organizations that carry out, fund, and evaluate research, we commit to the following:

1

We will make openness the default for the research information we use and produce

- Openness will be the norm for the research information we use, for instance to assess researchers and institutions, to support strategic decision making, and to find relevant research outputs.
- Openness will be the norm for the research information we produce, for instance information about our activities and outputs, with an exception for information for which openness would be inappropriate ('as open as possible, as closed as necessary').

Barcelona Declaration - Commitment 2

2

We will work with services and systems that support and enable open research information

- For publishing services and platforms, we will require that research information generated in publication processes (e.g., metadata of research articles and other outputs) be made openly available through open scholarly infrastructures, using standard protocols and identifiers where available.
- For systems and platforms for the internal management of research information (e.g., current research information systems), we will require that all relevant research information can be exported and made open, using standard protocols and identifiers where available.

Barcelona Declaration - Commitment 3

3

We will support the sustainability of infrastructures for open research information

- We take responsibility for supporting infrastructures for open research information, for instance by participating in community building and community governance and by providing fair and equitable contributions to the financial stability and development of these infrastructures.
- We expect the infrastructures that we support to implement good practices for community governance and sustainability (e.g., Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure).

Barcelona Declaration - Commitment 4

4
We will support collective action to accelerate the transition to openness of research information

- We recognize the importance of sharing experiences and coordinating action to promote a system-wide transition from closed to open research information.
- To facilitate this, we support establishing a Coalition for Open Research Information and strengthening collaboration with other related initiatives and organizations.

Joint roadmap

Topics and actions

1. Journal article metadata

- Develop a **framework for open publication metadata** (incl. for books) including a list of the most important metadata elements for journal articles and books.
- Organize a **gap analysis** based on the developed framework
- Develop **principles for community control** over publication metadata (incl. for books)
- Demand in **future negotiations with publishers** the deposition of comprehensive metadata to infrastructure providers (e.g., Crossref, DataCite), preferably using PIDs, and monitor delivery
- Create **affordable ways for poorly-resourced publishers to start using PIDs** (e.g. DOIs) and to start making metadata openly available

2. Metadata in IR, data en preprint repositories

- Share **experiences of giving credit to authors and other staff members** for sharing data/code and improving metadata quality
- Draft **guidelines to create and use linked research objects**
- Propose **guidelines about human resources** to dedicate to metadata validation/moderation in IRs
- Pilot **implementing a machine-learning pipeline** to detect datasets and software from full-text.

3. Funding metadata

- Organize a **workshop with vendors, publishers and funders** to discuss the **minimum requirements for how the submission system** should support the registration of grant metadata and the progression through the system to registration.
- **Expanding the use of existing systems for metadata management** amongst a wider and more geographically distributed group of funders.
- Produce a **set of resources to show how funders are making grant metadata available** for advocacy and for improving the use of standards

4. Replacing closed systems

- Develop and distribute a survey, to make an **inventory of user stories**, and all Barcelona Declaration signatory organizations will have the results ready
- Create guidelines that **prioritize research outputs with persistent identifiers** (handle or not handle), encouraging any indexing service to have equal access to these products.
- Set a **minimum quality standard for data submitted to PIDs' operators**.
- Scientometrics and relevant management teams at signatory organizations have **access to required training** to support the active use of open research information. Monitor uptake and usage of resources.
- Identify at least 20 organizations that are willing to sign a **statement to unsubscribe from the closed data sources**.
- **Include currently missing provenance information** in Open Research Information Resources (e.g., source of data, whether it has been reviewed/curated) and make filters available for users.

5. Sustaining infrastructures

- Information sharing on **how open research infrastructures and resources are supported** yearly
- Survey of signatories to know **how much is spent on proprietary tools and resources**
- **Produce a model & guidelines** of what they need , want and expect from open research information infrastructure -> how it can translate to supporting
- Adopt and agree on a model guideline of required open research information services/systems
- **Contribute to an endowment pool** over a ten year period with a governance entity that could support infrastructure sustainability
- **Commit to redirecting funding saved** from cancellation of closed services to directly support open infrastructure providers rather than returning savings to institutional overhead

6. Evaluating open data sources

- Agree on a **set of criteria for open research information sources** with a focus on minimal requirements that support adoption
- Develop a **set of reporting guidelines** for evaluations
- Support projects for **developing evaluation tools and methods**
- Implement evaluation tools and methods in a **monitoring framework**

7. Evidence of benefits

- Collect **case studies of use of signatories' open research information** by the public
- Produce a **stakeholder map and a taxonomy of benefits**
- **Map costs, inequities and other undesirable effects** of closed systems
- Engage with journal editors to launch an open call for a **special issue about the benefits of open research information**
- Identify, develop and implement actions to **improve multilingual metadata and other forms of bibliodiversity.**

Open Research Information: Input from the Helmholtz Open Science Office

Marc Lange

Helmholtz Association, Helmholtz Open Science Office

Helmholtz Open Science Forum on Open Research Information

April 2, 2025

Barcelona Declaration Open Science Office's Activity So Far

April 2024	Barcelona Declaration released
June/July 2024	Start of coordination and early consultations within Helmholtz
September 2024	Paris Conference on Open Research Information
October 2024	Establishment of community of practice in DACH region
November 2024	Planning of potential activities and events Coordination of participation in working groups
February 2025	Start of Barcelona Declaration's working groups
April 2025	Forum - today
May 2025	Bologna Meeting on Open Research Information

Barcelona Declaration

Participation in Working Groups

- 1 Journal article metadata & book metadata
- 2 Metadata on research outputs in institutional repositories, preprint and data repositories
- 3 Funding metadata
- 4 Replacing closed systems
- 5 Sustaining infrastructures
- 6 Evaluating open data
- 7 Evidence of benefits

Research Information in Helmholtz Status Quo

All Helmholtz centers generate, collect, use and provide research information.

- Research information is generated and collected naturally as part of administration.
- Research information is used in evaluations and for various other (strategic) processes.
- Research information on publications (incl. data/software) is provided via repositories.
- Some Centers operate CRIS for the dedicated provision of research information.

→ Open research information is not entirely new.

- Some of the Barcelona Declaration's objectives are already met to a certain degree.
- Potential for improvement and for a more coordinated and knowledge-based approach?
- In the Helmholtz Open Science Policy, the aspect of open research information has not yet been explicitly mentioned, but is an important point of reference for the defined open science principles.

→ Gather more information on the centers' states regarding research information.

Barcelona Declaration

Meeting the commitments

1

We will make openness the default for the research information we use and produce

- Openness will be the norm for the research information we use, for instance to assess researchers and institutions, to support strategic decision making, and to find relevant research outputs.
- Openness will be the norm for the research information we produce, for instance information about our activities and outputs, with an exception for information for which openness would be inappropriate ('as open as possible, as closed as necessary').

Barcelona Declaration

Meeting the commitments

2

We will work with services and systems that support and enable open research information

- For publishing services and platforms, we will require that research information generated in publication processes (e.g., metadata of research articles and other outputs) be made openly available through open scholarly infrastructures, using standard protocols and identifiers where available.
- For systems and platforms for the internal management of research information (e.g., current research information systems), we will require that all relevant research information can be exported and made open, using standard protocols and identifiers where available.

Barcelona Declaration

Meeting the commitments

3

We will support the sustainability of infrastructures for open research information

- We take responsibility for supporting infrastructures for open research information, for instance by participating in community building and community governance and by providing fair and equitable contributions to the financial stability and development of these infrastructures.
- We expect the infrastructures that we support to implement good practices for community governance and sustainability (e.g., Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure).

Barcelona Declaration

Meeting the commitments

4

We will support collective action to accelerate the transition to openness of research information

- We recognize the importance of sharing experiences and coordinating action to promote a system-wide transition from closed to open research information.
- To facilitate this, we support establishing a Coalition for Open Research Information and strengthening collaboration with other related initiatives and organizations.

Barcelona Declaration

What are Other Institutions Doing?

- Focus on the institution's own infrastructures and the openness and opening of its own research information and CRIS, i.e. the side of the production and provision of research information
- Promoting and implementing more use of open research information sources, e.g. OpenAlex.
- Links to research assessment and their activities in this respect, e.g. joining CoARA.
- Yet few and limited statements on moving away from closed, proprietary data sources and systems and switching to open data sources and systems, although processes have been initiated at many institutions on this issue.

Barcelona Declaration

What Are Other Institutions Doing?

Barcelona Declaration

What Are Other Institutions Doing?

Long term

- Seriously **consider the use of and need for 'commerical black boxes'** such as Pure, Web of Science, Scopus and others.

Barcelona Declaration

What Are Other Institutions Doing?

The image is a screenshot of a news article from Sorbonne University. At the top left is the Sorbonne University logo, which consists of a stylized 'S' with a building icon inside, followed by the text 'SORBONNE UNIVERSITÉ'. To the right of the logo is a navigation menu with the following items: 'EDUCATION', 'RESEARCH', 'INTERNATIONAL', 'CAMPUS LIFE', 'UNIVERSITY', a search icon, and a user profile icon labeled 'YOU ARE'. Below the navigation menu is a breadcrumb trail: 'Home * News * Sorbonne University unsubscribes from the Web of Science'. The main content area has the sub-header 'Open Science' in italics. The main title is 'Sorbonne University unsubscribes from the Web of Science' in a large, bold, black font. Below the title is a short paragraph: 'Sorbonne University has been deeply committed to the promotion and the development of open science for many years. According to its commitment to open research information, it has decided to discontinue its subscription to the Web of Science publication database and Clarivate bibliometric tools in 2024. Research data and online theses of open access publications are available on the university's open access platform.' To the right of the text is a large, colorful illustration. It features a central, complex, geometric structure resembling a molecular model or a network graph, with various icons and objects floating around it, including a giraffe, a butterfly, a globe, a book, a person, and a building. The background is a light green grid pattern.

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Open Science

Sorbonne University unsubscribes from the Web of Science

Sorbonne University has been deeply committed to the promotion and the development of open science for many years. According to its commitment to open research information, it has decided to discontinue its subscription to the Web of Science publication database and Clarivate bibliometric tools in 2024. Research data and online theses of open access publications are available on the university's open access platform.

Open Research Information Points of Reference and Potentials

- Research assessment (and making it more transparent, open and equitable)
- Strategic policy decisions
- Sovereignty
- Cost reductions / making funds available for open infrastructures

Open Research Information Challenges

- Data tracking
- Research security
- Opening too much information and harm funding prospects
- New vendor lock-ins?
- Funding of data sources

→ *as open (and extensive) as possible, as closed (and limited) as necessary*

Thank you for your attention!

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Open Infrastructures for open Research Information

KIT-Library, Department for Publication & Media Services

Open Science at Helmholtz

Digitization opens up the opportunity for science to change the way it handles data, information, and knowledge.

At Helmholtz, the term **open science**, outlining a cultural change in scientific working methods and communication, is defined as follows:

"The open - meaning impeded by as little financial, technical, and legal obstacles as possible - access to scientific results such as publications, research data, and research software expands transparency in academia, improves quality assurance procedures, and through improved supply of information increases the productivity of academia. Open science thus always also serves the improvement of good scientific practice. Furthermore, open science fosters knowledge transfer into society, economy, and politics."

Publish in Open Access Infrastructures @ KIT

- KIT-Library runs different scholar-led publication infrastructures under open access model
- distribution of science is in the hands of KIT and researchers, far from commercial distributors

KITopen

 Scientific
Publishing

*The ideal publication
service at the KIT for
my project.*

Central Data Turntable: Repository KITopen

→ Worldwide connection to Open-Access-Services and Databases
→ Open-Access-Verification is filled in automatically

<https://publikationen.bibliothek.kit.edu/kitopen/login/>

Personalized research profile

My KITopen

+ Deposit

Deposit media

Q Search

Search form

Own search queries

My media

Media checked by myself

Media entered by myself

All publications of institute BIB

? Help

Your media in your profile

What can I contribute?

1. Check your own media for correct assignment
2. Upload and deposit your own media
3. Update your media with additional research information

Personification

Central media list

Nexus to
ORCID-Profile

Diamond OA Services – Take data in your hands

- This service offers a professional platform for scientific journals together with publishing partner Ubiquity Press
- We support the founding of new journals and with flipping existent journals to scholar-led infrastructures
- Based on the Diamond-Open-Access-Model the publication costs will be beared institutionell or from societies

Project ERRED

- DFG paper ["Wissenschaftliches Publizieren als Grundlage und Gestaltungsfeld der Wissenschaftsbewertung"](#) (May 2022). => Content should be given greater consideration in research evaluation than the place of publication. "Cultural Change"
- Develop a transferable reference model for reporting based on DORA
- A set of indicators will be developed that works beyond journal-based metrics and takes an open and transparent look at the breadth of research performance. In addition to textual publications, for example, research data and research software are also taken into account
- Based on the model for the new Helmholtz quality indicator for research data and software products

Where does Future take us?

Open bibliometrics – Reporting

- KIT has a huge amount of publications (research data...)
- The Helmholtz context demands a constant reporting metrics
- How can we provide a new approach for reporting?
- Idea: multidimensional analysis which allows a qualitative view on research

Leitprojekt „Open Science and FIS light“ at KIT

- Part of the KIT „Dachstrategie 2025“
- Two components
 - Research information system as mainly *internal* tool for management information and reporting
 - General open science policy for KIT; supplementing the Helmholtz OS-policy

And how about, DORA, CoARA and Barcelona Declaration?

Signed

Under discussion

BARCELONA
DECLARATION ON
OPEN RESEARCH
INFORMATION

To be discussed (that's what we are her for ;-)

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